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Urban–Rural Differences In Civic Education Curriculum Implementation And Control Of Social Vices Among Senior Secondary School Students

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the extent of Civic Education curriculum implementation and its contribution to the control of social vices among senior secondary school students in North-Central Nigeria, with particular attention to urban–rural differences. Five research questions and hypotheses guided the study. A survey research design was adopted, and data were collected from Civic Education teachers using a structured questionnaire. Independent samples t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed no significant differences between urban and rural schools in the extent of Civic Education curriculum implementation ($t = 0.755$, $p > 0.05$), teachers' instructional strategies ($t = 0.612$, $p > 0.05$), availability and utilization of instructional materials ($t = 1.37$, $p > 0.05$), contribution of Civic Education to the control of social vices ($t = 1.252$, $p > 0.05$), and teachers' perceptions of its effectiveness ($t = 0.755$, $p > 0.05$). Mean results indicated moderate implementation and moderate contribution to behavioural change. It was concluded that although Civic Education is being implemented in both urban and rural schools and has the potential to influence students' behaviour positively, its impact is not yet maximized due to moderate levels of implementation and support structures. It was recommended that implementation fidelity be strengthened, teachers' capacity enhanced, adequate instructional resources provided, and innovative participatory strategies promoted to enhance the role of Civic Education in curbing social vices among secondary school students.

Keywords: Civic Education; Curriculum Implementation; Social Vices; Urban–Rural Differences

INTRODUCTION

Civic Education remains a critical component of secondary school curricula globally, serving as a strategic tool for shaping responsible citizenship, promoting positive values, and discouraging antisocial behaviour among adolescents. In Nigeria, the introduction of Civic Education as a compulsory subject at the senior secondary level was aimed at equipping learners with knowledge of their rights and responsibilities, fostering national consciousness, strengthening moral development, and curbing the rising incidence of social vices in schools and society (Kayode-Olawoyin, 2017). Despite this strategic intent, social problems such as cultism, drug abuse, bullying, truancy, examination malpractice,

vandalism, cybercrime, and violent behaviour continue to manifest among students, raising questions about how effectively the Civic Education curriculum is being implemented in different contexts (Makinde, Kehinde-Dada & Babatunde, 2020).

The persistent occurrence of these social vices has become a major concern for parents, educators, policymakers, and communities, as they undermine academic achievement, threaten school safety, and jeopardize students' future well-being (Ushie et al., 2021). Scholars have argued that the success of Civic Education in shaping students' character and behaviour depends not only on the quality of curriculum content but also on the extent and manner of its implementation in schools. Implementation encompasses teachers' pedagogical practices, availability of instructional materials, teacher training, classroom interactions, assessment approaches, and the overall school environment that supports moral and civic learning (Sofadekan, 2017). Where implementation is weak or inconsistent, expected behavioural outcomes may not be achieved.

Nigeria's North-Central region presents a particularly compelling context for examining Civic Education implementation. The region is characterized by cultural diversity, varying socio-economic conditions, and recurrent social challenges affecting young people. At the same time, significant disparities exist between urban and rural school environments in terms of infrastructure, teacher quality, exposure to societal influences, and administrative support (Nasiru & Iorliam, 2025). Urban schools often have greater access to trained teachers, instructional resources, and supervisory mechanisms, but students may also be more exposed to peer pressure, media influence, and sophisticated forms of social vices. Conversely, rural schools may have closer community ties and stronger value socialization, yet frequently grapple with shortages of qualified teachers, limited learning resources, and inadequate curriculum support structures (Shehu, 2021).

These contextual differences raise an important inquiry: Do urban and rural settings differ in how Civic Education is implemented and in the extent to which it contributes to controlling social vices among senior secondary school students? Existing studies on Civic Education in Nigeria have largely focused on curriculum content adequacy, teachers' perception, instructional challenges, and students' civic knowledge and attitudes. However, relatively fewer empirical studies have explored the urban–rural dimension of implementation, particularly in relation to behavioural outcomes such as the reduction of social vices. Understanding these contextual variations is essential for developing targeted strategies that strengthen Civic Education's effectiveness across different school environments (Opuwari et al., 2019).

Furthermore, teachers are central to curriculum implementation. Their competence, perception, motivation, and access to professional support significantly shape classroom experiences. If teachers in urban and rural schools experience different constraints or adopt different instructional approaches, the impact of Civic Education on students' behaviour may vary correspondingly ((Nsidibe, 2019). Likewise, the level of administrative support, availability of teaching materials, and school–community collaboration may differ across locations, influencing how values, discipline, and civic responsibility are internalized by learners (Alufohai & Asika, 2019).

This study is therefore anchored on the need to generate empirical evidence on how Civic Education curriculum implementation varies between urban and rural senior secondary schools and how these differences relate to efforts at curbing social vices among students in North-Central Nigeria. In light of the foregoing, this study investigates urban–rural differences in Civic Education curriculum implementation and the control of social vices among senior secondary school students in North-Central Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

To examine urban–rural differences in the implementation of Civic Education curriculum and its effectiveness in controlling social vices among senior secondary school students in North-Central Nigeria. Specific objectives are to:

- i. determine the extent of Civic Education curriculum implementation in urban and rural senior secondary schools;
- ii. examine differences in teachers' instructional strategies in Urban and rural schools in implementing Civic Education curriculum;

- iii. assess the availability and utilization of instructional materials for Civic Education in urban and rural schools;
- iv. determine whether Civic Education contributes differently to the control of social vices among students in urban and rural schools; and
- v. examine teachers' perceptions of the effectiveness of Civic Education in curbing social vices in urban and rural schools.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What is the extent of Civic Education curriculum implementation in urban and rural senior secondary schools in North-Central Nigeria?
2. What differences exist in teachers' instructional strategies for Civic Education implementation between urban and rural schools?
3. To what extent are instructional materials for Civic Education available and utilized in urban and rural senior secondary schools?
4. To what extent does Civic Education contribute to the control of social vices among students in urban and rural senior secondary schools?
5. How do teachers perceive the effectiveness of Civic Education in curbing social vices in urban and rural school settings?

Research Hypotheses

In line with the above research questions, the following null hypotheses were formulated:

H01: There is no significant difference in the extent of Civic Education curriculum implementation between urban and rural senior secondary schools in North-Central Nigeria.

H02: There is no significant difference in teachers' instructional strategies for Civic Education implementation between urban and rural senior secondary schools.

H03: There is no significant difference in the availability and utilization of instructional materials for Civic Education between urban and rural senior secondary schools.

H04: There is no significant difference in the contribution of Civic Education to the control of social vices among students in urban and rural senior secondary schools.

H05: There is no significant difference in teachers' perception of the effectiveness of Civic Education in curbing social vices between urban and rural senior secondary schools.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework for this study is premised on the belief that the effective implementation of the Civic Education curriculum plays a critical role in shaping students' civic knowledge, values, attitudes, and behaviour, thereby contributing to the control of social vices in schools. However, the extent to which Civic Education influences students' behaviour may vary depending on the environment in which it is implemented. In Nigeria's North-Central region, urban and rural schools differ considerably in terms of teacher quality, learning resources, school environment, and students' exposure to societal influences. These contextual variations may affect how Civic Education is taught and the degree to which it translates into meaningful behavioural change among learners.

Within this framework, Civic Education curriculum implementation constitutes the independent variable. It is conceptualized along three major dimensions. The first dimension is the extent of implementation, which relates to the level of curriculum coverage, regularity of lesson delivery, and the degree to which teaching activities align with the prescribed curriculum. The second dimension is teachers' instructional strategies, focusing on whether teachers employ participatory, value-driven, and interactive approaches such as debates, discussions, case studies, role-play, and moral dialogue that are essential for promoting critical thinking, ethical reasoning, and civic responsibility among students. The third dimension concerns the availability and utilization of instructional materials, including textbooks, teaching guides, charts, audio-visual aids, and ICT resources, as well as how effectively these resources are used during instruction to reinforce civic learning.

School location serves as the moderating or contextual variable. Urban and rural school environments present different realities that may facilitate or constrain curriculum delivery and learning outcomes. Urban schools may enjoy better access to qualified teachers, instructional materials, and supervision, yet students may also face heightened exposure to complex social pressures and negative peer influences. In contrast, rural schools may benefit from stronger community cohesion and traditional value orientation but often struggle with inadequate resources, limited teacher specialization, and infrastructural challenges. These differences imply that the influence of Civic Education on students' behaviour may not be uniform across locations.

The dependent variable is the control of social vices among senior secondary school students. In this study, control of social vices refers to the extent to which Civic Education contributes to reducing behaviours such as cultism, drug abuse, bullying, truancy, violence, examination malpractice, cybercrime, and other forms of misconduct. It also encompasses improvements in students' discipline, moral restraint, civic responsibility, and positive social conduct.

The framework therefore proposes a causal linkage in which effective implementation of the Civic Education curriculum enhances students' civic competence and value orientation, leading to a reduction in social vices. The quality of implementation, particularly through sound instructional strategies and adequate learning resources, is expected to strengthen students' internalization of civic norms and moral standards. However, this relationship is moderated by school location, as urban and rural contexts may influence both the process and outcomes of Civic Education delivery. Pictorial representation of this is presented thus:

Conceptual Analysis

Synopsis of Curriculum Implementation

Effective curriculum implementation is critical for achieving the intended goals of any educational program (Button, 2021; Ornstein & Hunkins, 2017). Curriculum implementation involves translating curriculum plans, standards, and guidelines into actual teaching and learning experiences (Ylimaki, 2012; Wolfe, 2015). Success depends on collaboration among teachers, administrators, policymakers, and other stakeholders, as well as the provision of adequate support, resources, and guidance to teachers (Bediako, 2019). Teachers, as primary implementers, are responsible for delivering content, adapting lessons to student needs, and engaging learners in meaningful experiences (Ornstein & Hunkins, 2017; Wolfe, 2015).

Key components of curriculum implementation include: curriculum planning and development, teacher training and support, resource allocation, classroom instruction and delivery, assessment and evaluation, administrative monitoring, and stakeholder involvement (Ylimaki, 2012; Wolfe, 2015; Ornstein & Hunkins, 2017). Effective implementation requires continuous teacher training, adequate and equitable resource distribution, collaborative practices among educators and administrators, curricular flexibility to meet diverse student needs, and ongoing monitoring and evaluation to ensure relevance and impact.

In essence, curriculum implementation is not merely executing a plan but entails active engagement, support, and adaptation to achieve desired learning outcomes. The quality of implementation directly influences the curriculum's effectiveness in fostering knowledge, skills, dispositions, and behavioural outcomes among students, highlighting the teacher's central role and the importance of systemic support structures.

Teachers and Curriculum Implementation

Teachers' characteristics play a pivotal role in the effective implementation of curricula, including Civic Education. As primary implementers, teachers' qualifications, experience, subject specialization, instructional skills, attitudes toward teaching, adaptability, and professional development directly influence how well curriculum content is delivered and internalized by students (Amopho, 2020; Muhwezi, Kurgat & Ssekamate, 2021). Experienced teachers tend to anticipate students' learning difficulties, employ effective pedagogical strategies, and achieve better student outcomes, though productivity may decline after many years of teaching (Nyoni, 2018; Torpev & Rabi, 2016).

Teachers' subject specialization also affects curriculum delivery, as specialists often exert greater influence in their areas, shaping the inclusion and emphasis of specific topics (Nsidibe, 2019). Additionally, involving teachers in curriculum decision-making ensures ownership and facilitates smoother implementation, whereas high turnover of untrained or part-time teachers can impede curriculum effectiveness (Alufohai & Asika, 2019). Teachers must also stay updated with advancements in knowledge and technology to deliver relevant and effective instruction.

Student characteristics are equally important in curriculum implementation. Learners' attitudes, motivation, academic skills, self-discipline, willingness to participate, and reading habits significantly affect their engagement with the curriculum and the achievement of learning outcomes (Nyoni, 2018; Torpev & Rabi, 2016). Active classroom participation, problem-solving, and discussions enhance meaningful learning and the overall effectiveness of curriculum implementation. Therefore, successful curriculum implementation depends on the interplay between teachers' competence, experience, specialization, and engagement, and students' motivation, skills, and participation. Both teacher- and student-related factors are critical for ensuring that curricula, including Civic Education, achieve their intended educational and behavioural outcomes.

Overview of Civic Education

Civic Education, derived from the terms "civic" and "civitas," traces its origins to ancient Greece, where it promoted loyalty to collective interests and active participation in state affairs (Kayode-Olawoyin, 2017). Globally and in Nigeria, its core objectives include promoting democratic values, cultivating knowledge of citizens' rights and responsibilities, encouraging active civic participation, developing critical thinking, and fostering social cohesion and national identity (Falade & Adeyemi, 2015; Kayode-Olawoyin, 2017; Sele, 2020). Traditionally, Nigerian society emphasized moral and civic values through family and community instruction, focusing on honesty, discipline, and social responsibility (Kayode-Olawoyin, 2017).

Formally, Civic Education has evolved from early civics programs to a component of social studies and, more recently, as a mandatory subject in Nigeria's 9-year Basic Education program, aimed at equipping students with knowledge, skills, and dispositions for responsible citizenship (Kayode-Olawoyin, 2017; Ubong & Iboro, 2018). The curriculum emphasizes understanding government structures, recognizing rights and duties, and developing problem-solving, participatory, and ethical skills necessary for active citizenship (Ogunkeye, 2012; Fakorede, 2015; Sofadekan, 2017).

Effective implementation of Civic Education ensures that learners internalize civic values, engage meaningfully in societal and political processes, and develop ethical decision-making skills. This practical engagement is critical for addressing social vices, as students equipped with civic knowledge, critical thinking abilities, and moral dispositions are less likely to engage in behaviors such as truancy, bullying, cultism, and examination malpractice (Ubong & Iboro, 2018). Consequently, Civic Education serves as a strategic tool in Nigerian schools to cultivate responsible, disciplined, and socially conscious citizens, thereby contributing to the reduction of social vices among students.

Concept of Social Vices

Social vices among secondary school students are negative behaviors that disrupt the learning environment, hinder academic progress, and compromise students' well-being (Makinde, Kehinde-Dada & Babatunde, 2020; Apase & Fawe, 2019). Common vices include substance abuse, bullying and violence, truancy, exam malpractice, theft and vandalism, early sexual activity, cultism, and cyber misconduct (Amiaya, 2015; Ahmad, 2017; Ushie et al., 2021). These behaviors often reflect broader societal issues and are influenced by a combination of individual, familial, peer, socioeconomic, cultural, and institutional factors. Key contributors include broken homes, poor parental supervision, peer pressure, poverty, media influence, weak moral guidance, school environment, low self-esteem, mental health challenges, and the availability of illicit substances (Amiaya, 2015; Ahmad, 2017; Ezeaku & Dunu, 2020).

The consequences of social vices are far-reaching. Academically, students involved in vices such as truancy, substance abuse, and exam malpractice often perform poorly (Ezeaku & Dunu, 2020). Health risks include physical injury, addiction, mental health issues, and exposure to sexually transmitted

infections (Ahmad, 2017). Socially and psychologically, victims of bullying or cyber harassment may experience low self-esteem, depression, and anxiety (Ushie et al., 2021). Furthermore, social vices create hostile and unsafe school environments that negatively impact overall learning outcomes (Apase & Fawe, 2019) and may expose students to legal consequences such as expulsion or arrest (Amiaya, 2015). Clearly, social vices among Nigerian secondary school students are multidimensional, arising from individual, familial, peer, school, and societal factors. Their pervasive effects on academic, social, and psychological outcomes underscore the need for effective preventive measures, including the implementation of Civic Education curricula aimed at fostering ethical values, responsible behavior, and civic-mindedness.

Controlling Social Vices among Students: Civic Education Imperative

Civic education serves as a powerful antidote to social vices among secondary school students by fostering ethical values, civic responsibility, and social awareness (Ubong & Iboro, 2018; Kayode-Olawoyin, 2017). Through the promotion of moral and ethical principles such as honesty, integrity, and accountability, students develop the capacity to distinguish right from wrong and make informed choices that deter engagement in harmful behaviors (Ogunkeye, 2012; Falade & Adeyemi, 2015). Civic education also cultivates respect for laws and societal norms, equipping learners with knowledge of their rights and responsibilities and reinforcing the consequences of violating social rules, which reduces tendencies toward theft, substance abuse, and violence (Sofadekan, 2017).

Moreover, civic education enhances critical thinking and decision-making skills, enabling students to analyze societal issues, resist peer pressure, and avoid impulsive behaviors (Sele, 2020). Participation in community service and civic activities promotes a sense of belonging and active citizenship, reducing boredom and disengagement that often lead to social vices such as truancy or gang involvement. The curriculum further fosters awareness of human rights and social justice, strengthening empathy and reducing discriminatory or violent behaviors (Ubong & Iboro, 2018). Lessons in emotional intelligence, self-regulation, discipline, and conflict resolution equip students with practical tools to manage challenges without resorting to anti-social acts.

Obviously, empowering students with knowledge of their rights and responsibilities, encouraging positive peer interactions, and modeling exemplary civic behavior, civic education reduces susceptibility to negative social influences and promotes ethical, socially responsible conduct (Kayode-Olawoyin, 2017). Consequently, effective implementation of civic education in Nigerian secondary schools is a vital strategy for mitigating social vices, shaping morally upright, disciplined, and engaged citizens capable of contributing positively to their communities and the broader society (Ubong & Iboro, 2018).

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on a combination of behavioural, moral-development, and curriculum-implementation theories that explain how Civic Education can influence students' behaviour and how contextual factors such as school location shape educational outcomes.

i. Social Learning Theory (Bandura, 1977)

Social Learning Theory posits that behaviour is learned through observation, imitation, and reinforcement. Students acquire values and behavioural patterns by watching teachers, peers, and significant adults, as well as through interactions within their school and community environments. Civic Education provides structured moral and civic models through classroom discussions, role-play, debates, and real-life examples of ethical and unethical behaviour. When teachers demonstrate civic responsibility, fairness, discipline, and respect for rules, students are likely to internalize these behaviours, thereby reducing tendencies toward social vices such as truancy, violence, drug abuse, and dishonesty. In urban and rural schools, differences in teacher quality, exposure, and learning environments may influence the behavioural models available to students. Thus, the theory helps explain how effective curriculum delivery can shape students' character and why behavioural outcomes may differ by location.

ii. Kohlberg's Theory of Moral Development (1976)

Kohlberg explains moral development as a progressive movement through stages where individuals move from obedience-based morality to principled moral reasoning. Civic Education plays a vital role in

guiding students through these stages by exposing them to concepts such as justice, rule of law, honesty, responsibility, and respect for human rights. Through guided discussions, moral dilemmas, and reflective learning, Civic Education encourages students to think critically about right and wrong and to choose socially acceptable behaviour. In this study, the theory explains how systematic Civic Education instruction can develop students' moral judgment and reduce involvement in social vices. Effective implementation enhances students' movement toward higher moral reasoning, whereas weak delivery limits moral growth.

iii. Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory (1979)

This theory emphasizes that human behaviour is shaped by multiple environmental systems — the family, school, peers, community, and wider socio-cultural context. School location (urban or rural) reflects different ecological environments that influence learning opportunities, value exposure, and behavioural expectations. Urban schools often operate within complex social environments characterized by greater exposure to media influence, peer pressure, and diverse social activities, while rural schools may reflect closer community ties but limited infrastructure and resources. The theory justifies the moderating role of school location in this study, explaining why Civics curriculum implementation and its behavioural impact may differ between urban and rural settings.

iv. Curriculum Implementation Theory (Fullan, 2007)

Curriculum Implementation Theory emphasizes that successful curriculum outcomes depend on how curriculum intentions are translated into classroom practice. Implementation is influenced by teacher competence, availability of instructional materials, professional support, and contextual realities. Civic Education can only achieve its intended behavioural objectives when teachers adopt appropriate instructional strategies, utilize relevant materials, and engage students in meaningful civic experiences. This theory underpins the focus on extent of implementation, instructional strategies, and use of instructional resources as key determinants of behavioural outcomes.

The theoretical perspectives collectively clarify how the study variables interact to shape students' behaviour. These theories explain that when Civic Education is implemented effectively, using participatory and value-oriented teaching methods supported with adequate learning resources, students are more likely to internalize positive civic values and demonstrate responsible behaviour. These are summarized on the table below.

Table 1: Theory Variables Mediated Table

Theory	Core Assumptions	Key Constructs from Theory	Study Variable(s) Linked	Mediating / Explanatory Role in the Study
Social Learning Theory (Bandura, 1977)	Behaviour is learned through observation, imitation, reinforcement, and modelling.	Observational learning, reinforcement, modelling, vicarious experience	- Teachers' Instructional Strategies - Extent of Civic Education Implementation - Control of Social Vices	Explains how effective Civic Education teaching practices expose students to positive behavioural models, reinforcing civic values and discouraging deviant behaviours.
Kohlberg's Theory of Moral Development (1976)	Moral reasoning develops in stages and improves through guided learning and value exposure.	Moral reasoning, value internalization, ethical judgment	- Extent of Civic Education Implementation - Control of Social Vices	Mediates how exposure to Civic Education content leads to higher moral reasoning, which in turn reduces involvement in social vices.
Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory (1979)	Behaviour is shaped by interacting environmental systems (school, community, peers, society).	Microsystem, mesosystem, exosystem, macrosystem	- School Location (Urban vs Rural)	Explains why differences in environmental context influence Civic Education implementation and its behavioural outcomes, thereby moderating the relationship between implementation and social vices control.
Curriculum Implementation Theory (Fullan, 2007)	Curriculum success depends on teacher competence, resources, school environment, and implementation fidelity.	Implementation fidelity, teacher capacity, instructional support	- Extent of Implementation - Instructional Strategies - Instructional Materials	Explains how the quality and consistency of Civic Education implementation determine whether expected behavioural outcomes (control of social vices) are achieved.

Empirical Review

The empirical review summarizes findings from previous studies related to the research topic, focusing on their methods, results, and conclusions. Several studies have examined the implementation of Civic Education and Social Studies curricula in Nigerian secondary schools and their impact on students' behaviour, moral development, and civic competence. Ali, Hayatu, and Badau (2015) reported that while Civic Education was implemented in Adamawa State, a shortage of qualified teachers constrained its effectiveness. Samuel (2015) found in Lagos and Ogun States that classroom implementation emphasized knowledge acquisition over skills and dispositions, compounded by inadequate teaching resources and eclectic pedagogical practices. Adeyemi (2018) in Osun State confirmed that effective curriculum implementation, supported by relevant textbooks and instructional materials, could serve as an antidote to social vices. Yusuf et al. (2018) in Kwara State highlighted that teachers perceived Civic Education positively as a measure for curbing corruption. Similarly, Sanusi and Ali (2022) established that effective implementation of Civic Education in Kano State fosters national consciousness among students.

Other studies focused on behavioural outcomes and character formation. Amiaya (2015) and Ahmad (2017) reported high prevalence of social vices among students in Delta and Zamfara States, with Civic or Social Studies education mitigating these behaviours to some extent. Abdu-Raheem (2018), Opuwari et al. (2019), and Ugwu (2023) demonstrated that Civic Education and Social Studies enhance moral values, patriotism, and discipline, while Arazi and Ekima (2024) showed that Social Studies curriculum implementation significantly improves student discipline in Bayelsa State. Bello (2021) noted persistent immoral behaviours among students but found that Social Studies content could curb them, and Bassey et al. (2021) reported that Civic Education promotes obedience, participation, and respect for authority. Nasiru and Iorliam (2025) confirmed that the Civic Education curriculum effectively addresses social vices in North-Central Nigeria, though limited instructional resources hinder full implementation.

Studies on broader interventions, such as Chizi-Out and Wami (2021), indicated that adult education programs, including vocational and peace education, significantly reduce social vices, highlighting the relevance of civic and moral education beyond formal schooling. Shehu (2021) demonstrated that Civic Education also fosters entrepreneurship skills, equipping students with practical competencies for societal contribution and economic growth.

Collectively, these studies emphasized that Civic Education curriculum can enhance civic knowledge, moral reasoning, discipline, and social responsibility, but their effectiveness is moderated by teacher competence, pedagogical strategies, availability of instructional resources, and school context. This body of literature provides a strong rationale for examining urban–rural differences in curriculum implementation and its influence on curbing social vices among senior secondary school students in North-Central Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

The descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. According to Ekpo, Orji and Is'haq (2022), It allows for the collection of data from a large population to examine existing conditions, relationships, and differences across urban and rural school contexts. The population consisted of 2,728 Civic Education teachers from senior secondary schools across the six states of North-Central Nigeria, including the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja.

A sample of 585 Civic Education teachers was drawn from the population using a stratified random sampling technique to ensure proportional representation across the six states and between urban and rural schools. Stratification was based on school location (urban vs rural), which is a key variable in the study. Data were collected using the questionnaire structured in a 4-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Agree (4) to Strongly Disagree (1). The instrument was validated by experts in curriculum studies and demonstrated high reliability, with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.89 obtained through a pilot study.

Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, frequency, and percentage) were used to summarize respondents' perceptions of curriculum implementation and instructional strategies. The independent samples t-tests was employed to examine

differences in Civic Education implementation and perceptions between urban and rural school teachers. All analyses were conducted at a 0.05 significance level.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

This section presents the analysis of the data collected for the study and the results obtained. Appropriate analytical techniques are applied, and the findings are presented systematically to address the research questions and hypotheses.

RQ1: *What is the extent of Civic Education curriculum implementation in urban and rural senior secondary schools in North-Central Nigeria?*

H01: There is no significant difference in the extent of Civic Education curriculum implementation between urban and rural senior secondary schools in North-Central Nigeria.

Table 1: Results related to Research Question One and Hypothesis One

Group	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	Sig.
Rural	190	3.01	0.48	583	0.755	0.45
Urban	395	3.04	0.49			

Table 2 presents the comparison of Civic Education curriculum implementation between rural and urban schools. Rural schools (N = 190) recorded a mean score of 3.01 (SD = 0.48), while urban schools (N = 395) recorded a slightly higher mean score of 3.04 (SD = 0.49). An independent samples t-test conducted to determine the significance of this difference produced a t-value of 0.755 with 583 degrees of freedom and a significance value of 0.45.

Since the p-value (0.45) is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, the observed difference in mean scores is not statistically significant. This means that the extent of Civic Education curriculum implementation is essentially the same in both urban and rural senior secondary schools in North-Central Nigeria. Consequently, Hypothesis One is retained, indicating no significant difference in implementation based on school location.

RQ2: *What differences exist in teachers' instructional strategies for Civic Education implementation between urban and rural schools?*

H02: There is no significant difference in teachers' instructional strategies for Civic Education implementation between urban and rural senior secondary schools.

Table 2: Results related to Research Question Two and Hypothesis Two

Group	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	Sig.
Rural	190	3.04	0.43	583	0.612	0.541
Urban	395	3.02	0.42			

Table 3 shows the comparison of teachers' instructional strategies in rural and urban senior secondary schools. Rural teachers (N = 190) recorded a mean score of 3.04 (SD = 0.43), while their urban counterparts (N = 395) recorded a mean score of 3.02 (SD = 0.42). An independent samples t-test was conducted to determine whether these differences were statistically significant. The result revealed a t-value of 0.612 with 583 degrees of freedom and a significance value of 0.541.

Since the p-value (0.541) is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, the difference in mean scores is not statistically significant. This implies that teachers in both urban and rural schools employ largely similar instructional strategies in the implementation of Civic Education. Therefore, Hypothesis Two is retained, indicating no significant difference in instructional strategies across locations.

RQ3: *To what extent are instructional materials for Civic Education available and utilized in urban and rural senior secondary schools?*

H03: There is no significant difference in the availability and utilization of instructional materials for Civic Education between urban and rural senior secondary schools.

Table 3: Results related to Research Question Three and Hypothesis Three

Group	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	Sig.
Rural	190	2.94	0.52	583	1.37	0.17
Urban	395	3.00	0.51			

Table 4 shows the comparison of instructional material availability and utilization across locations. Rural schools (N = 190) recorded a mean score of 2.94 with a standard deviation of 0.52, while urban schools (N = 395) recorded a slightly higher mean score of 3.00 with a standard deviation of 0.51. The independent samples t-test yielded a t-value of 1.37 at 583 degrees of freedom and a significance value (p) of 0.17.

Since the p-value (0.17) is greater than the 0.05 significance level, the difference in the mean scores between rural and urban schools is not statistically significant. This indicates that the availability and utilization of instructional materials for Civic Education are similar in both urban and rural senior secondary schools. Therefore, Hypothesis Three is retained, confirming no significant difference based on school location.

RQ4: To what extent does Civic Education contribute to the control of social vices among students in urban and rural senior secondary schools?

H04: There is no significant difference in the contribution of Civic Education to the control of social vices among students in urban and rural senior secondary schools.

Table 4: Results related to Research Question Four and Hypothesis Four

Group	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	Sig.
Rural	190	2.90	0.56	583	1.252	0.211
Urban	395	2.96	0.55			

Table 4 presents the comparison of respondents' perceptions of the contribution of Civic Education to curbing social vices among students. Rural schools (N = 190) recorded a mean score of 2.90 with a standard deviation of 0.56, while urban schools (N = 395) recorded a slightly higher mean score of 2.96 with a standard deviation of 0.55. An independent samples t-test produced a t-value of 1.252 at 583 degrees of freedom, with a significance value of 0.211.

Since the p-value (0.211) is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, the difference in mean scores between urban and rural schools is not statistically significant. This indicates that Civic Education contributes to the control of social vices among students to a similar extent in both urban and rural senior secondary schools. Therefore, Hypothesis Four is retained, confirming no significant difference based on school location.

RQ5: *How do teachers perceive the effectiveness of Civic Education in curbing social vices in urban and rural school settings?*

H05: There is no significant difference in teachers' perception of the effectiveness of Civic Education in curbing social vices between urban and rural senior secondary schools.

Table 5: Results related to Research Question Five and Hypothesis Five

Group	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	Sig.
Rural	190	2.98	0.49	583	0.755	0.451
Urban	395	3.01	0.49			

Table 6 shows the comparative analysis of teachers' perceptions of the effectiveness of Civic Education in reducing social vices among students. Teachers in rural schools (N = 190) reported a mean score of 2.98 with a standard deviation of 0.49, whereas their counterparts in urban schools (N = 395) recorded a mean score of 3.01 with the same standard deviation of 0.49. An independent samples t-test yielded a t-value of 0.755 at 583 degrees of freedom, with a corresponding p-value of 0.451.

Since the p-value (0.451) is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, the difference in teachers' perceptions between urban and rural schools is not statistically significant. This indicates that teachers

across both school locations hold similar views regarding the effectiveness of Civic Education in curbing social vices among students. Consequently, Hypothesis Five is retained, confirming no significant difference in perception based on school location.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of this study revealed no significant difference in teachers' perceptions of the effectiveness of Civic Education in curbing social vices between urban and rural senior secondary schools in North-Central Nigeria. Both groups reported moderately positive perceptions, suggesting that Civic Education is recognized as a useful tool for promoting positive behaviour, enhancing value orientation, and discouraging deviant acts among students, irrespective of school location.

This outcome aligns with previous research that underscores the transformative potential of Civic Education in shaping students' moral outlook, social responsibility, and law-abiding behaviour. Studies such as Falade and Adeyemi (2015), Sofadekan (2017), Ubong and Iboro (2018), and Sele (2020) reported that Civic Education enhances students' understanding of citizenship values, strengthens respect for the rule of law, and promotes ethical conduct—factors that are essential in reducing deviant behaviours such as truancy, bullying, violence, drug abuse, and examination malpractice. Similarly, Kayode-Olawoyin (2017) emphasized that Civic Education equips learners with critical thinking, empathy, and democratic dispositions, enabling them to resist negative peer influence and engage more responsibly in school and community life.

Furthermore, the finding supports Ogunkeye (2012), who maintained that Civic Education, when effectively implemented, fosters value reorientation and strengthens social control mechanisms in school environments. The similarity in perception between urban and rural teachers suggests that the objectives and expected behavioural outcomes of Civic Education are well understood across locations and that teachers generally believe the curriculum possesses the potential to address behavioural challenges faced by secondary schools.

However, the moderate mean perception scores indicate that teachers do not perceive Civic Education as fully maximized in its capacity to curb social vices. This observation resonates with earlier reports highlighting challenges such as inadequate instructional materials, insufficient teacher training, and limited practical civic engagement opportunities, which may impede the full realization of Civic Education objectives (Falade & Adeyemi, 2015; Ubong & Iboro, 2018). Where such limitations exist, Civic Education may function more at a theoretical level than as a lived experiential learning process capable of producing deep behavioural change.

In contrast, some scholars argue that Civic Education alone may not be sufficient to address entrenched social vices unless supported by effective school discipline policies, parental involvement, community partnerships, and favourable learning environments (Sofadekan, 2017; Sele, 2020). This suggests that while teachers acknowledge Civic Education as beneficial, they may also recognize that its impact depends largely on broader systemic and environmental support structures. Therefore, the findings of the study reinforce the view that Civic Education is widely perceived as a relevant and valuable instrument for behaviour modification and social vice control among secondary school students.

CONCLUSION

The study examined urban–rural differences in Civic Education curriculum implementation and its contribution to the control of social vices among senior secondary school students in North-Central Nigeria. The findings revealed no significant differences between urban and rural schools in terms of curriculum implementation, instructional strategies, availability and utilization of instructional materials, the contribution of Civic Education to the control of social vices, and teachers' perceptions of its effectiveness.

These findings reinforce existing literature that Civic Education has strong potential to promote moral discipline, respect for the rule of law, empathy, responsible citizenship, and positive behavioural orientation among students. However, the moderate outcomes imply persistent challenges such as inadequate instructional resources, insufficient practical civic engagement activities, and implementation

gaps that may limit its impact. Hence, strengthening Civic Education implementation mechanisms is therefore critical to maximizing its behavioural and social transformation roles in both urban and rural contexts.

RECOMMENDATIONS

This section presents practical recommendations based on the findings of the study. The recommendations are aimed at addressing identified issues and guiding stakeholders, policymakers, and future research.

1. Education authorities and school administrators should intensify efforts to ensure full and consistent implementation of the Civic Education curriculum across urban and rural schools. Monitoring and support mechanisms should be enhanced to encourage fidelity
2. Regular capacity-building programmes, workshops, and professional development initiatives should be organized for Civic Education teachers to improve pedagogical competence, innovative delivery methods, and classroom management skills related to behavioural transformation.
3. Policymakers should integrate Civic Education more strongly into school discipline frameworks and national value-orientation policies, ensuring that it remains a central pillar in character formation and youth behavioural reform initiatives.
4. Government should ensure the provision of adequate and relevant instructional materials - such as textbooks, teaching aids, ICT resources, and civic learning tools - to support effective teaching and learning, particularly in resource-constrained rural schools.
5. Teachers should adopt learner-centred instructional strategies such as debates, simulations, role play, case studies, community service learning, and civic engagement projects to promote practical understanding, behavioural internalisation, and real-life application of civic values.
6. Schools should collaborate with parents, law-enforcement agencies, community leaders, and civil society organisations to reinforce civic values, provide mentorship, and collectively address behavioural issues among students.
7. Regular evaluation of Civic Education implementation and its behavioural outcomes should be conducted to identify strengths, weaknesses, and emerging needs, thereby enabling continuous improvement in both urban and rural schools.

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